

Quantifying single-event aircraft noise: a calibrated LMax model for Dublin Airport North Runway departures

A single-event noise companion to the EIDW EIA-Conformance Gap Analysis
(Zenodo 10.5281/zenodo.19567671)

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Public debate about Dublin Airport's North Runway (28R) departure noise is conducted almost entirely in long-term average metrics (Lden, Lnight), which conceal what residents actually experience: the peak level of each individual overflight. This paper builds a per-aircraft-type single-event LMax model for 28R departures, calibrated directly on the airport operator's own noise-monitor data. Using 364,831 correlated noise-monitor events released by daa under access-to-information request AIE 2611 (1 March 2025 to 28 February 2026), we fit a per-type propagation law that reproduces the measured peak levels to about 2 dB RMS across the full 300 m to 2,600 m range the monitor network samples, and which cross-validates when fitted near the runway and tested on the farther events it never saw. We then render single-event LMax footprints for the common fleet on the two flown departure arms, validated against the operator's own monitor medians, and contrast them with counterfactual footprints flown along the routes assessed in the 2004/2005 Environmental Impact Statement. The single-event levels are stark: at Kilcoskan National School the operator's own monitor records a median peak of 74.6 dBA, with 92% of events above 70 dBA and 167 events per day, against the roughly 50 to 53 dBA Lden figure commonly cited in public discussion. The school is directly under the flown northern departures yet about 2.5 km from the nearest route the Environmental Impact Statement assessed.

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1 Introduction

The point of this paper is simple: the noise people hear from a departing aircraft is its single-event peak, and that peak is being hidden behind annual averages.

Dublin Airport's noise reporting, and the public conversation around it, is dominated by L_{den} and L_{night} , energy-averaged metrics that smear a year of operations into a single contour band. A location described as "in the 55 dBA L_{den} band" is routinely mistaken for, or mischaracterised as, "the aircraft are 55 dBA when they pass." The two differ by roughly 20 dB, which the ear perceives as about four times as loud, since each 10 dB of level is heard as a doubling of loudness. The metric that captures the lived experience of an overflight, the loudest instant as the aircraft passes, is L_{Amax} , and it is rarely published per type or per route.

This confusion has a mathematical root, and it is the source of much of the misunderstanding in public debate. The decibel is a logarithm of an energy ratio, and L_{den} and L_{night} average that energy over a whole year, so both the scale and the headline metrics are quantities in the energy domain. Human loudness is not: a listener perceives roughly a doubling of loudness for every 10 dB increase, however the underlying energy was averaged. The two treatments diverge sharply, and the gap is repeatedly exploited or misread, with a long-run energy-averaged band figure presented as the level a resident hears as each aircraft passes. The single-event peaks recorded on daa's own monitors make the difference concrete: a median L_{Amax} of about 74 dBA for a 28R departure (Section 2), roughly 20 dB, or two perceived doublings, above the 50 to 53 dBA figures commonly cited for these overflights in public debate. On the ground, as a single event, the aircraft are on the order of four times as loud as those figures imply.

This paper supplies that missing layer. It is the single-event noise companion to the GIS impact study (the EIDW EIA-Conformance Gap Analysis, Zenodo 10.5281/zenodo.19567671), which quantified the population within the overflown and affected corridors; that study reserved a single-event noise footprint as the basis for its 3 km affected-corridor half-width and pointed to this deposit for the derivation. Here we build the single-event L_{Amax} model, calibrate it on the regulator's own measurements, validate it, and apply it to the actual departure routes, to notable individual overflights, and to the counterfactual routes the original Environmental Impact Statement assessed.

2 Data

2.1 Noise-monitor events (AIE 2611, daa)

The calibration rests on daa's own noise-monitor terminal (NMT) data, released in full under AIE 2611 (decision 1 May 2026). The release comprises a correlated-event table of 364,831 28R-departure events over the twelve months to 28 February 2026, one row per (monitor, flight) pairing, carrying date/time, monitor location, aircraft type, flight number, tail number, the peak level (LAmox, the `Max Level` field), SEL, Leq, and the operator-computed geometry at the moment of peak: height, slant distance, ground range and elevation angle relative to the monitor; and a companion table of the 27 active monitor locations spanning the communities under the 28R departure routes.

Three properties of the data, confirmed directly, matter for what follows.

First, the values are single-event peaks, not averages. The three noise columns are internally consistent: `Max Level` (median 73.9 dBA) is always at least `Leq` (median 69.9), `SEL` (median 83.8) is always at least `Max Level`, and `SEL` minus `Leq` equals $10 \log_{10}(\text{duration})$ to the decibel (14.3 dB against a 27 s median duration), the textbook identity that can only hold if `Max Level` is the instantaneous peak and `Leq` the event-mean. So the figures throughout are directly comparable to single-event LAmox bands, not to `Lden` or `Lnight`.

Second, the geometry is aircraft-to-monitor, not aircraft-to-route. We verified that $\text{slant}^2 = \text{ground}^2 + \text{height}^2$ holds across the data (median reconstructed height 2,025 ft against reported altitude 2,024 ft, computed elevation 47.8 deg against reported 48.0 deg). The slant distance is therefore the propagation path length from aircraft to receiver, the correct variable for a propagation law, and carries no information about lateral offset from the SID centreline.

Third, the dataset is bounded by a 2,500 m correlation criterion, codified in writing by daa for the first time in this release: a noise event is attributed to a flight only if the aircraft passed within 2,500 m of the monitor. We confirmed it: maximum ground range 2,650 m, 95th percentile 1,434 m, median 600 m; only 3 of 364,831 events exceed 2,500 m ground range. The consequence, central to Section 6, is that the data densely samples the near field and is silent beyond 2,500 m.

2.2 Departure tracks (ADS-B)

Aircraft ground tracks and climb profiles come from FlightAware ADS-B (AeroAPI), used to construct the route geometry for the footprint model. Because runway direction follows the wind, only westerly (28R) operating days are usable for the northern departure arms; days were selected by EIDW METAR wind direction. The contributor-tier API serves only the last ten days of history, which constrains the sample (see Section 6) and precludes joining the ADS-B to the AIE 2611 noise events, which lie outside that window.

EIDW 28R departures by SID route group: ADS-B 25-26 Mar 2026 (n=271 tracks; 31 turboprops, 1 flight-inspection excluded)

Figure 1: EIDW 28R departures by SID route group (ADS-B, 25 to 26 March 2026), over the 27-monitor network. A common stem over St Margaret’s and Ward splits into the straight arm (northwest, to Ratoath) and the DW128-right arm (north, then east of Ashbourne toward the coast). Arms are assigned by the same waypoint-and-heading test the footprint composites use (Section 3.4); turboprops, which the model excludes, and a navaid flight-inspection sortie are omitted.

2.3 Population context

Settlement context is the CSO Census 2022 Built-Up Areas layer (population field T1_2T) and OpenStreetMap residential building footprints for the study extent. These provide the “where the people are” backdrop and the named places; they are not part of the noise calibration.

3 Methods

3.1 Propagation law and per-type calibration

We model the single-event peak level at a receiver as a point source decaying with slant distance r by spherical spreading plus a linear atmospheric-absorption term:

$$L(r) = L_{\text{ref}} - 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right) - \alpha r \quad (1)$$

where $r_0 = 305$ m (1,000 ft) is the reference distance, L_{ref} the per-type source level at r_0 , and α an absorption coefficient (dB/m). The $-20 \log_{10}$ term is inverse-square (free-field) spreading; αr lumps atmospheric absorption and any distance-proportional excess attenuation.

For each aircraft type we estimate L_{ref} and α by ordinary least squares over that type's N events, minimising

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \left(L_i - [L_{\text{ref}} - 20 \log_{10}(r_i/r_0) - \alpha r_i] \right)^2, \quad (2)$$

which is linear in L_{ref} and α once the spreading term is moved to the left. The fit is therefore an ordinary least squares regression in the decibel domain: the measured LAmox values are fitted directly, never collapsed to an average, so the distinction between arithmetic and energy (logarithmic) averaging of decibels does not enter the calibration. Every measured level reported below is likewise a median, not a mean, robust and order-preserving. (A variant fixes α at a field-anchored 0.5 dB/km and fits L_{ref} alone; it changes L_{ref} by under 2 dB and is used only for sensitivity.) Turboprops are excluded: their source characteristics do not follow the jet slant law (fit residuals near 4 dB).

Table 1 gives the fitted parameters. The fits are tight for the jet fleet, about 2 dB RMS, and the decay runs steeper than pure spherical spreading (22 to 29 dB per decade), consistent with the absorption term.

Figure 2: Measured single-event LAmax versus slant distance for the 737-800 (112,736 events, hex-binned by event count), with the fitted propagation law of Eq. 1 (red). The decay runs steeper than free-field spreading, and the events terminate at daa’s 2,500 m correlation limit.

Table 1: Per-type calibration (Eq. 1), AIE 2611 events, 1 Mar 2025 to 28 Feb 2026. L_{ref} at 305 m slant. {#tbl:calib}

Type	Aircraft	n events	L_{ref} (dBA)	α (dB/km)	fit RMS (dB)
B738	737-800	112,736	86.4	1.67	2.07
A320	A320ceo	64,820	86.3	2.39	2.07
B38M	737 MAX 8	50,649	81.7	0.95	1.97
A21N	A321neo	19,131	83.4	1.49	2.20
A333	A330-300	18,189	91.8	3.09	2.60
A20N	A320neo	16,227	81.6	1.11	2.62
B763	767-300F	6,187	89.4	2.54	2.71

Type	Aircraft	n events	L_{ref} (dBA)	α (dB/km)	fit RMS (dB)
B789	787-9	5,041	85.2	2.24	1.91
B772	777-200	3,575	91.1	3.84	2.06
B764	767-400ER	767	93.6	3.91	2.38

3.2 Cross-validation of the propagation law

To test that the law describes the data rather than merely fitting it, we withhold by geometry: estimate L_{ref} and α on the inner events alone ($r < 1,500$ m), then predict the outer events (1,500 m to $\sim 2,600$ m) the fit never saw, the direction of the far field. Table 2 reports the held-out error. For the high-volume types the law extrapolates well in distance (bias under 1 dB, RMS 2 to 3 dB); the small positive bias means it slightly under-predicts farther out, the conservative direction. The 737 MAX and A321neo extrapolate looser (RMS ~ 4 dB), a consequence of their small fitted α , which makes the inner-only fit a weaker predictor of the outer falloff; their full-data fits (Table 1) remain tight.

Table 2: Geometric cross-validation. Parameters fitted on the inner events ($r < 1,500$ m), error reported on the held-out outer events ($r \geq 1,500$ m, to $\sim 2,600$ m). {#tbl:xval}

Type	bias (dB)	RMS (dB)
B738	+0.56	2.51
A320	+0.49	2.92
A333	+0.47	2.15
B763	+0.90	2.80
B772	-0.25	1.99
B764	+0.85	1.89
B38M	+1.92	4.27

Type	bias (dB)	RMS (dB)
A21N	+1.33	4.12

We also test directly for lateral (ground) attenuation by binning the full-fit residuals by elevation angle (Table 3). The data spans the whole angular range, 0 to 90 degrees, because early in the climb an aircraft is low and to the side of a lateral monitor. At the low angles where lateral attenuation would appear (0 to 20 degrees) the residuals are slightly positive: the measured levels are if anything above the simple slant model, not below. There is no lateral-attenuation deficit anywhere the data reaches; the small angle-dependent structure (low angles a touch louder, overhead a touch quieter) is the opposite sign to attenuation and is consistent with ground reflection or source directivity.

Table 3: Mean fit residual (measured minus Eq. 1, dB) by elevation-angle band. {#tbl:resid}

Type	0-20°	20-30°	30-45°	45-90°
B738	+0.15	+0.47	-0.18	-0.13
A333	+1.44	+0.25	-0.02	-0.69

3.3 Footprint geometry (lateral extent of each band)

A footprint band is the ground area over which the single-event peak from a passing aircraft equals or exceeds a threshold T . For an aircraft at height h above ground, the level directly below follows from Eq. 1 with $r = h$:

$$L_0(h) = L_{\text{ref}} - 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{h}{r_0} \right) - \alpha h. \quad (3)$$

At a ground receiver offset laterally by y from the point under the aircraft, the slant path is $r = \sqrt{h^2 + y^2}$, so

$$L(y; h) = L_{\text{ref}} - 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\sqrt{h^2 + y^2}}{r_0} \right) - \alpha \sqrt{h^2 + y^2}. \quad (4)$$

The lateral half-width of the T -dBA band at height h , $w(h, T)$, is the offset y at which $L(y; h) = T$. Because of the absorption term this is transcendental and is solved numerically (bisection to convergence). The absorption-free case gives a closed-form upper bound used to bracket the search:

$$w_0(h, T) = h \sqrt{10^{(L_0(h)-T)/10} - 1}, \quad (5)$$

obtained by dropping α in Eq. 4 and solving the spreading term alone. Since absorption only steepens the falloff, $w(h, T) \leq w_0(h, T)$.

The footprint of a departure is then the swept band. Parameterising the (smoothed) track centreline by arc length s , with climb profile $h(s)$, the T -dBA contour is the set of ground points within $w(h(s), T)$ of the centreline, that is, the centreline buffered by a half-width that varies along track with the aircraft's height:

$$\mathcal{B}_T = \{ p : \text{dist}(p, \text{centreline}(s)) \leq w(h(s), T) \}. \quad (6)$$

The band is narrow and intense near the runway (low h , high L_0) and widens then fades as the aircraft climbs. Bands are drawn at 5 dB steps from 90 down to 55 dBA. Those at and above 65 dBA lie within the calibrated data; the 55 and 60 dBA bands are extrapolated (Section 6) and are drawn hatched and faded to mark that.

3.4 Composite departure tracks

For each aircraft type and arm we build one composite departure to carry $h(s)$ and the centreline. Members are the ADS-B departures that both overfly the arm's defining waypoint and made the arm's turn (established heading in range), excluding flights that merely clip the waypoint before flying elsewhere. At each step along track we take the inlier mean position (members within 2 km of the median, rejecting strays), then smooth at a 1 km scale so the result reads as a single composite trajectory rather than a jittery average; beyond the coherent section the

centreline is extrapolated straight ahead on the established heading. The climb profile $h(s)$ is the members' own averaged altitude. Track points are interpolated with an 8x parametric cubic spline before contouring.

3.5 Singletons

Individual notable overflights are rendered from a single real track (no averaging), reading the actual altitudes for the contour model, so the footprint reflects exactly how low that aircraft was. Tracks are taken from ADS-B or from FlightRadar24 KML exports.

3.6 Measured-annotation semantics

Where a footprint passes a monitor, we annotate the monitor with daa's measured median LAmox for that type. This is the per-type, per-monitor median over the AIE 2611 year, pooled across all routes: the event table carries aircraft type but no SID field, so the medians cannot be segmented by departure arm. For monitors only one arm passes near, the median is effectively that arm's traffic; for the common-stem monitors near the airport both arms contribute, mildly, because near the stem both fly the same initial geometry. The annotations are daa's measurements, independent of the model, which is what makes them a validation rather than a restatement; they are not single-flight values.

4 Results

4.1 Measured source levels

The fitted per-type source levels are given in Table 1. They span roughly 82 to 94 dBA at 305 m across the fleet, the wide-body types (A330, 767, 777) sitting some 5 to 10 dB above the narrow-body fleet, with a distance decay of 22 to 29 dB per decade. The fits hold to about 2 dB RMS on tens of thousands of events per common type, and they cross-validate (Section 3.2). These levels, calibrated on the operator's own measurements, are the source terms used in every footprint that follows.

4.2 Validation against the operator’s measurements

The model reproduces daa’s measured medians along the corridors. Where a composite corridor crosses a monitor, the modelled level and the operator’s printed median agree to within a decibel or two: over Kilcoskan National School the model puts the 737-800 about 77 dBA and the A330-300 about 83 dBA overhead, against daa’s measured medians of 76 and 81 dBA at that monitor. Combined with the geometric cross-validation (Section 3.2), the propagation law is corroborated both in functional form and against independent measurement.

Table 4 gives a sample of the operator’s measured per-type medians at four representative monitors. The fleet ordering is consistent across monitors: the A330-300 runs 5 to 7 dB above the narrow-body fleet at every location. These are per-type, per-monitor medians over the year, pooled across routes (Section 3.6).

Table 4: Sample measured median single-event LAmox (dBA), daa NMT, by type and monitor.
{#tbl:measured}

Monitor	B738	B38M	A320	A333
Kilcoskan Nat Sch	76.0	73.1	74.7	80.6
St Margaret’s Nat Sch	75.7	71.5	74.6	81.0
Newpark	76.1	72.0	75.7	81.3
Ratoath	66.7	63.6	66.2	72.6

4.3 Footprints on the flown routes

The composite footprints show the loud core (70 to 90 dBA) running as a tight corridor directly over the near-track communities, with the heavier types (A330, 767) producing markedly wider and louder cores than the narrow-body fleet. The A333 averages 91.8 dBA at source and reads 81 to 83 dBA measured at the schools, the “infrequent but loud” group.

Single-event LAmox footprint — B738, straight / Ratoath arm
 track = mean of 4 ADS-B departures; source level 86.4 dBA @305 m (AIE 2611 NMT calibration)

Figure 3: Single-event LAmox footprint, 737-800 on the straight (Ratoath) arm, composite of the flown departures. daa's measured median LAmox for the type is annotated at each monitor the corridor crosses.

Single-event LAmox footprint — B738, DW128-right arm (north, east of Ashbourne)
 track = mean of 27 ADS-B departures; source level 86.4 dBA @305 m (AIE 2611 NMT calibration)

Figure 4: Single-event LAmox footprint, 737-800 on the DW128-right arm (north, then east of Ashbourne).

Figure 5: Single-event LMax footprint, A330-300 on the straight arm: the loud, infrequent heavy. Source level 91.8 dBA; measured medians 81 to 83 dBA at the schools.

4.4 Singletons (individual notable overflights)

A genuine over-Ashbourne pass: Delta DL45, a Boeing 767-400, on 22 March 2026 passed 466 m from Ashbourne town centre at about 4,100 ft; the model puts roughly 76 dBA overhead at the town from that one aircraft. On 31 May 2026 two Aer Lingus departures crossed St Margaret's minutes apart on the same northwest arm: EIN127 (A330-300) at about 900 ft and EIN101 (A321neo) at about 1,000 ft, a loud heavy and a quieter narrow body on an identical track, illustrating how much aircraft type alone changes the single-event footprint.

Single-event LMax footprint — B764 DL45 (2026-03-22) over Ashbourne (B767-400)
single flight as flown; source level 93.6 dBA @305 m (AIE 2611 NMT calibration)

Figure 6: Single-flight footprint, Delta 767-400 (DL45) over Ashbourne at about 4,100 ft, 22 March 2026 (FlightRadar24 track). Source level 93.6 dBA; about 76 dBA overhead at the town.

Single-event LMax footprint — A333 EIN1EN (2026-05-31) (EIN127, A330-300, DUB-YYZ)
single flight as flown; source level 91.8 dBA @305 m (AIE 2611 NMT calibration)

Figure 7: Single-flight footprint, Aer Lingus A330-300 (EIN127) over St Margaret's at about 900 ft, 31 May 2026.

Single-event LMax footprint — A21N EIN10M (2026-05-31) (A21N, over the house)
 single flight as flown; source level 83.4 dBA @305 m (AIE 2611 NMT calibration)

Figure 8: Single-flight footprint, Aer Lingus A321neo (EIN101) on the same arm minutes later at about 1,000 ft, 31 May 2026: the quieter narrow body for comparison.

4.5 The EIS counterfactual

The routes assessed in the 2004/2005 Environmental Impact Statement depart west of the northern communities before turning to destination: the EIS B738 route stays 6.7 km from Ashbourne and 8.2 km from Ratoath, where the flown route passes 2.1 km from Ashbourne and 477 m from Ratoath, essentially overhead. The same gap appears at the receptor scale: the flown departures pass within a few hundred metres of Kilcoskan National School, while the nearest route the EIS assessed stays about 2.5 km from it. We render the EIS-route footprint for each type by carrying that type’s actual (turning-SID) averaged climb along the EIS centreline; because a straight EIS departure out-climbs a turning SID, this is conservative and overstates the EIS footprint. Even so, the EIS corridor peels away from the communities that the flown corridor crosses.

COUNTERFACTUAL: EIS-route LMax footprint — B738 (straight-arm destinations, turning-SID climb) if flown along the EIS-assessed route (never flown); source level 86.4 dBA @305 m (AIE 2611 NMT calibration)

Figure 9: Counterfactual: 737-800 on the EIS-assessed straight route (never flown), departing west of the communities before turning. Compare the flown corridor over Ratoath in the corresponding footprint above.

COUNTERFACTUAL: EIS-route LMax footprint — B738 (right-arm destinations, turning-SID climb) if flown along the EIS-assessed route (never flown); source level 86.4 dBA @305 m (AIE 2611 NMT calibration)

Figure 10: Counterfactual: 737-800 on the EIS-assessed eastbound route, departing west then looping east via ENDEQ, rather than the flown DW128-right turn over the communities.

5 Discussion

5.1 The metric the public is given is the wrong one

The headline finding is a measured rebuttal of the L_{den} conflation. At Kilcoskan National School, daa's own monitor records a median single-event L_{Amax} of 74.6 dBA; 0.0% of events fall below 53 dBA, 92% exceed 70 dBA, and there are 167 such events per day. The school lies about 2.5 km from the nearest route the Environmental Impact Statement assessed; it is overflown only because the routes as flown were turned over it. The roughly 50 to 53 dBA figure commonly cited for these communities is an L_{den} annual average, a different quantity by about 20 dB, roughly 150 times the sound energy and four to five times the perceived loudness. The averaging also hides frequency: the relevant burden is event peak times event count, both of which L_{den} suppresses.

More fundamentally, the averaged figure is not a usable proxy for what an overflight sounds like. The single-event peak is set by the aircraft type and its height on the day, and is close to constant per type whatever the traffic volume. The L_{den} and L_{night} values at a location instead rise and fall with the number of movements and the hours at which they occur, energy-averaged across a full year. Two locations with very different L_{den} bands can therefore experience near-identical peak levels as each aircraft passes, and a location in a comparatively low band still hears 70 to 75 dBA per overflight. The band figure describes the long-run energy accounting of a place; it does not describe, and cannot be read off as, the loudness of the event a resident reacts to.

This has a predictable effect on how the resulting complaints are received. A resident reporting a genuinely loud overflight is implicitly measured against an official figure of 50 to 53 dBA, a level associated with quiet daytime ambience, so the complaint is made to appear disproportionate to a problem the metric describes as minor. The disproportion is an artefact of the metric, not of the complaint: the event the resident is reacting to is, on the operator's own monitors, around 75 dBA. Whether the preference for an averaged headline metric over a single-event one is incidental or convenient, its effect is to discount the exposure it does not represent.

5.2 The far field is a validated extrapolation, not a guess

The 55 to 60 dBA bands lie beyond the 2,500 m envelope the data samples, but the propagation law that reaches them is validated across the full angular range and out to 2,600 m, with no lateral-attenuation deficit (Section 6). The extrapolated reach is therefore an upper bound (no attenuation means least falloff), which makes the GIS study's 3 km affected corridor conservative relative to the bare model.

6 Limitations

- **Far field.** The 55 to 60 dBA bands are extrapolated beyond the 2,500 m correlation envelope. The extrapolation is the continuation of a law validated in functional form (cross-validation) and across the full elevation range (no measured lateral-attenuation deficit), so it is semi-calibrated rather than free; but a distance-dependent ground attenuation growing in beyond 2,600 m cannot be ruled out from this data. The modelled reach is best read as an upper bound. We do not apply the standard ECAC Doc.29 lateral-attenuation term: the geometric cross-validation (Section 3.2) and the elevation-angle residuals (Table 3) already test directly for lateral attenuation across the full 0 to 90 degree range out to 2,600 m and find none, so imposing the term would lower the far-field levels against the measured evidence and forfeit the conservative upper-bound reading. Directly measured far-field points exist in daa's raw monitor recordings (the uncorrelated long-lateral triggers the 2,500 m rule discards) and could be recovered by a further access request.
- **Model form.** A single point-source level per type with slant-distance spreading and a lumped absorption term; no explicit directivity, ground reflection, flap or thrust-state terms. Adequate for relative single-event LMax footprints, not a regulatory dosage model.
- **Sparse types and arms.** The rarest heavies on the right arm (A333, B772 eastbound) had too few coherent ADS-B tracks in the available westerly days to form a composite.
- **No noise-to-track join.** The contributor-tier API's 10-day history precludes matching ADS-B to the AIE 2611 noise year, so measured levels cannot be placed at exact lateral offsets from the centreline.

7 Reproducibility

All inputs are archived with this deposit: the AIE 2611 records, the ADS-B departure pulls, the census and building layers. The calibration (`calibrate_nmt.py`), the per-monitor measured medians (`nmt_measured.py`), the footprint renderer (`render_lamax.py`) and the track overview (`render_overview.py`) regenerate every figure from those inputs. Methods and provenance are documented in `README.md`.

8 References

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